

BOOK OF ABSTRACTS OF DEMYSTICON 2025 BEYOND THE BIG BANG

Sesimbra Oceanfront Hotel, Sesimbra, Portugal

June 12 – 16, 2025

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Additional Special Grant from Jim & Bonnie Keller
Organized by DemystifySci
Dr. Anastasia V. Bendebury & Dr. Michael Shilo DeLay

“And the shields you see here
Instruct the tractable unending ocean:
The landlocked sea is Greek or Roman,
The boundless sea is Portuguese.”

Pillar Standard, 13-9-1918.
From Fernando Pessoa, Message, Portuguese Sea.

Translated and edited by Edwin Honig and Susan H. Brown
San Francisco: City Lights Books, 1998, p.187.
First published by The Ecco Press in 1986.

Original in Portuguese:

“E ao imenso e possível oceano
Ensinam estas Quinas, que aqui vês,
Que o mar com fim será grego ou romano:
O mar sem fim é português.”

Padrão, 13-9-1918.
From Fernando Pessoa, Mensagem, Mar português

Passage from a poem by the great 20th century Portuguese poet Fernando Pessoa,
read by André Assis and John Plaice the last evening at the conference.

Both thought that the reference to the boundless sea,
which they could admire from the terrace where everyone was seated,
was well suited for a conference entitled
“Beyond the Big Bang”.

Foreword by the Organizing Committee

It is our great pleasure to welcome all of you to Sesimbra, Portugal for DemystiCon 2025: Beyond the Big Bang. Our mission here is simple - a thorough exploration of the changing paradigms of astrophysics and cosmology. Our goal, too, is straightforward – though perhaps somewhat more ambitious. We hope to revive the intellectual foment of the old Royal Societies, where theorists, experimentalists, and philosophers can come together to refine their understanding of the hidden workings of nature.

First, some gratitude for those who have made this possible. Patrick Vanraes has done an incredible job of assembling this Book of Abstracts, for which we would already be forever grateful - but then he also organized multiple workshops for the weekend and is working on getting this weekend's proceedings into an official publication, which leaves us on the border of awe. Each of our speakers represents a bright star in the constellation of conversations we've hosted over the years, and we relish the opportunity hear their insights in person, rather than through the veil of Zoom. Jim Keller, one of the great architects of the computer revolution, is also an exceptional character in this pageant (and a generous patron of it!). When he is not reinventing the material basis of civilization, he somehow finds the time to trawl the anarchic fringes of the radical science that will be on display here this weekend. Finally, our supporters and attendees. We have the great fortune of meeting with you every week over Zoom, and are convinced that you are the greatest crew anywhere on the internet. When we started this project, we could not have imagined that five years later we would be sitting on the seaside in Portugal, about to go into our second conference with friends from all corners of the world.

At our first gathering, held one year ago in Austin, Texas, we celebrated the April 8th total solar eclipse with a weekend of talks about the foundations of nature. Like our podcast, this first gathering was broad in scope, an opening salvo for what we hoped would be a regular opportunity for our incredible community to explore the changing landscape of our favourite disciplines. This year, we happen to be celebrating the five year anniversary of the podcast, which was kicked off by an audio-only interview with David Lindley about his book, *The End of Physics*. Three hundred and forty three episodes later, it is fitting that our topic is what lies Beyond the Big Bang, and the non-standard cosmological theories that will help us navigate through the shifting landscape of standard cosmology.

At DemystiCon 2025, each day represents a different topic from astrophysics and cosmology. This Book of Abstracts includes contributions from 17 invited talks and 18 submitted poster presentations, in addition to the panel discussions and other activities planned during the five days of the conference. We are happy to receive attendees from at least 10 countries of at least 4 continents in our ever-growing community, and look forward to sharing the weekend with our remote audience.

All that said, we wish everyone an excellent and enlightening experience at DemystiCon 2025: Beyond the Big Bang. Let's dig in!

Dr. Anastasia Bendebury and Dr. Michael Shilo Delay
DemystiCon 2025 Organizing Committee Chairs

Foreword by the Publication Committee

First and foremost, I want to thank Anastasia and Shilo for inviting me to DemystiCon 2025 and giving me the opportunity to curate this Book of Abstracts. More than ever, there seems to be a strong need for alternative communication platforms in science – and cosmology in particular – where unconventional theories can readily be shared. In my view, it is exactly such diverse ideas that form the cornerstones of unprecedented and potentially ground-breaking new directions in scientific research. In the standard setting of modern academia, fresh perspectives tend to go unheard or struggle to find an audience due to peer pressure and closed prepublication review. Anastasia and Shilo do not only provide an alternative communication platform for these ideas, they also specifically seek to foster a community of the intellectually curious: academics, mavericks, contrarians, nonconformists and independent thinkers. In this way, the lone scientists of today no longer have to be alone and their voices no longer remain silenced.

With this collection of abstracts, I hope to give a broader reach to these voices, so they may be heard as well within the standard scientific community with a higher probability. The planned Roadmap article for non-standard cosmology and astrophysics, further discussed in my abstract E-2 and the afterword at the end of this Book of Abstracts, adds to this purpose. My gratitude goes to all DemystiCon 2025 participants for their enthusiastically written and non-written contributions. This conference promises to become a historic event, marking a new beginning to the cosmological dialogue. Without you, it would not have been complete.

Dr. Patrick Vanraes
DemystiCon 2025 Publication Committee Chair

DemystifySci Presents DemystiCon 2025

Anastasia & Shilo created the DemystiCon series as part of a longer, ongoing project to make sense of complex phenomena and discover the theories that they believe might transform the future. DemystifySci also produces a bi-weekly conversational podcast (The DemystifySci Podcast), where the two host discussions with elite thinkers from all corners of the curious world. They also produce the monthly series, Paradigm Drift, where any theorist alive can sign up for the chance to present their idea in one minute or less, and be interviewed briefly by the two and their guest panelist. Finally, Shilo & Anastasia are hard at work on a material science approach to fundamental physics. Initially, their musings were posted on YouTube (@MaterialAtoms), but the work is presently in preparation for publication in an upcoming book, soon to be available everywhere, called *Paradox Lost*. DemystifySci is entirely supported by the finest fleet of patrons the world has ever known.

Organizing Committee

Chair Anastasia Bendebury (DemystifySci / Southern Oregon University)

Anastasia is a scientist, writer, philosopher, and explorer, whose work focuses on the nature of life and the metaphysics of science and society. Following a fruitful career in research biology where she published on reproductive medicine, aging, tuberculosis, she received a PhD from Columbia University for her work on bioelectrical signalling in structured microbial communities. She is the co-creator of The DemystifySci Podcast, a twice weekly show that searches for the theories that may change the world. Her science writing has been published in *Discover*, *Astronomy*, and *Nautilus*, and she occasionally teaches medical microbiology at Southern Oregon University, guides wilderness backpacking trips in the Pacific Northwest, and is one half of the nymph rock band *Secretary of Nature*.

Chair Michael Shilo Delay (DemystifySci / Southern Oregon University)

Shilo has been obsessed with the atom since he was a child and first asked a grownup how gravity worked. He has published in biology and physics, most recently in nanoscale mechanics, earning a PhD from Columbia University in 2017. He now teaches astronomy, astrophysics and cosmology at Southern Oregon University, produces DemystifySci, and creates mythical music with overdriven guitars, or anything else that makes sound. Check out his songs on Spotify, Bandcamp or wherever you stream music (Shilo DeLay, Secretary of Nature).

Publication Committee

Chair Patrick Vanraes (University of Antwerp)

Patrick likes creating things, from drafts of dreams and written word combinations to social activities and lasting memories. At DemystiCon 2025, he wants to combine his experience as a former CouchSurfing ambassador with his passion for science and philosophy, by editing this Book of Abstracts and taking the first steps towards a Roadmap for the DemystifySci community. For this, he abides by the gladiator's battle cry, that "What we do in life echoes in eternity."

Invited Speakers

Keynote Eric J. Lerner (LPPFusion)

Eric J. Lerner is Chief Scientist of [LPPFusion](#), a leading fusion-energy R&D company. He has been active in astrophysics and cosmology for over 40 years and is the author of *The Big Bang Never Happened*. He has linked the study of plasmas in the cosmos with that of fusion plasmas, especially in the Dense Plasma Focus device. In the course of this work, he has developed and tested

against observations theories of quasars, of the origin of large-scale structures, light elements and the CMB. Together with colleagues, he has shown that galaxy surface-brightness data refutes cosmic expansion.

- Keynote** **Martín López-Corredoira (Instituto de Astrofísica de Canarias)**
Martín López-Corredoira (1970-; Spain) obtained doctorates in Physics at the University of La Laguna (Tenerife, Canary Islands, Spain) in 1997 and Philosophy at the University of Seville (Spain) in 2003. He is staff researcher at the 'Instituto de Astrofísica de Canarias' (IAC, Tenerife) working in the fields of galaxies and cosmology, and has published more than 130 papers in major astrophysical journals (ApJ, AJ, A&A, MNRAS, IJMPD mainly), about half of them as first author. He is author of the monography "*Fundamental Ideas in Cosmology. Scientific, philosophical and sociological critical perspectives*" (2022, IOP Publishing).
- Invited** **Andre Koch Torres Assis (University of Campinas)**
Andre Koch Torres Assis is a professor of physics at the University of Campinas - UNICAMP in Brazil, where he also obtained his undergraduate and PhD degrees. He works with cosmology, relational mechanics and implementation of Mach's principle, Weber's electrodynamics, and history of physics. His papers and books are available on his homepage:
<https://www.ifi.unicamp.br/~assis>
- Invited** **Indranil Banik (University of Portsmouth)**
Indranil Banik is a postdoc at ICG Portsmouth, where he works with Dr. Harry Desmond on testing the local void solution to the Hubble tension. He did his undergraduate and masters degrees in Cambridge and his PhD in Saint Andrews. He then did a three year Humboldt fellowship with Pavel Kroupa in Bonn, before returning to Saint Andrews. Indranil has conducted detailed tests of Milgromian dynamics (MOND), which encountered extremely serious difficulties in 2024:
<https://theconversation.com/is-dark-matters-main-rival-theory-dead-theres-bad-news-from-the-cassini-spacecraft-and-other-recent-tests-228826>
Indranil has advocated the local void scenario since 2019. He has also supervised many early career researchers over the years.
- Invited** **Mike McCulloch (University of Plymouth)**
Mike McCulloch gained a BSc in physics in 1991 and a PhD in ocean physics (physical oceanography) in 1995. He worked as an ocean and wave modelling scientist at the UK Met Office between 1998 and 2008, then became a lecturer in geomatics (the mathematics of positioning in space) at the University of Plymouth. He has published 27 peer-reviewed papers proposing and testing a new cosmological model for inertia (called quantized inertia, QI) that predicts galaxy rotation without dark matter and propellant-less propulsion. In 2018 he won \$1.3M from DARPA to test this new propulsion method. Four labs have now seen thrust and a test is being conducted in space. He has written two text books about QI theory: 'Physics from the Edge' (2014) and Quantised Acceleration (2024) and two sci-fi novels: 'Falling Up' (2021) and Hacking the Cosmos (2023). He is now an independent researcher and writer.

- Invited **Gareth Samuel (See the Pattern)**
Gareth Samuel is a former physics teacher turned independent researcher, exploring gaps in our understanding of cosmology and fundamental science. Through his YouTube channel “See the Pattern”, he analyzes patterns in data, questions standard interpretations, and revisits the insights of early pioneers in electrical and plasma research. His work critically examines modern and historical anomalies, with a recent focus on the limitations of the Big Bang model. A supporter of Plasma Cosmology, he acknowledges its challenges but sees value in its ideas. His aim is not to promote a single model, but to broaden discussion by highlighting alternative perspectives and uncertainties.
- Invited **C. S. Unnikrishnan (Defense Institute of Advanced Technology)**
C. S. Unnikrishnan is a professor at the Defence Institute of Advanced Technology (DIAT), Pune, India. He has been at the Tata Institute of Fundamental Research (TIFR), Mumbai during 1993-2022., and a visiting researcher at the Kastler-Brossel Laboratory (ENS) Paris, and at the University of Paris 13.
Unnikrishnan’s research interests are experimental and theoretical aspects of foundational issues in gravity and quantum physics. His theoretical contributions are the Theory of Cosmic Relativity, and a Universal Action Mechanics that solves the foundational problems of quantum mechanics. Unnikrishnan was a member of the LIGO Scientific Collaboration that detected gravitational waves. He has published about 250 scientific papers and two monographs.
More details are at <https://sites.google.com/view/unniPHY> and at [https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/C.S. Unnikrishnan](https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/C.S._Unnikrishnan). Some lecture videos are available in his YouTube channel @cs_unni
- Invited **Alexander Unzicker (Pestalozzi-Gymnasium München / The Machian)**
Alexander Unzicker holds diplomas in physics and law, as well as a PhD in Neuroscience. His debut book (English Edition: "Bankrupting Physics," Macmillan 2013) was honored with the "Science Book of the Year" award by "Bild der Wissenschaft." While he is best known for his critique of modern science (with works including "The Higgs Fake," "Make Physics Great Again," and "The Liquid Sun."), his primary interest lies in fundamental physics and its century-old unsolved problems, topics he also explores on his YouTube channel, "The Machian."
- Invited **Patrick Vanraes (University of Antwerp)**
Patrick Vanraes is a plasma physicist, engineer and philosopher of science with a persistent fascination for the unknown. His research expertise is almost as diverse as his interests, ranging from applied studies on water treatment by means of plasma technology and the computational modelling of plasma etching processes to fundamental investigations on plasma-liquid interaction, in-liquid plasma generation, the physics of liquid matter and phase transitions. In addition to his research papers, he wrote several reviews and perspective articles on many of these topics, two of which were awarded as Featured Articles and one of which as an Editor’s Pick.

Poster Presenters

Poster **Gary Barham (The Alchemist Studio)**

Gary Barham has been a researcher of esoteric mysticism and alchemy for over thirty-five years and was born in one of the last pieces of paradise on earth, New Zealand. He brings a true understanding of primordial nature together with a knowledge of our modern technological age. His research focus currently lies in the ‘new science’ including an investigation into what awaits us after the coming paradigm shift. He has recently released his first book, Quantum Geometry, and now lives in The Netherlands together with his alchemical partner and co-creator Christine and 3 cats.

Poster **Robin Booth (University of Sussex)**

Robin Booth is an independent cosmology researcher, whose main area of interest is in developing alternatives to the Λ CDM Big Bang paradigm. He gained a BSc in Physics from the University of Bristol, UK, in 1974. From 1999-2001 he undertook a MSc in Theoretical Physics at Imperial College London, UK. He has presented papers on Machian General Relativity, the Exochronous Universe, the static universe model, and alternatives to the Hubble redshift, at numerous international conferences and seminars, including the 2nd Crisis in Cosmology Conference. He was awarded a MPhil in Cosmology from the University of Sussex in 2024.

Poster **Wayne H. Coste (Unaffiliated)**

Wayne H. Coste is a Professional Engineer who has been licensed in the state of Michigan since 1983; he is a life member of the Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers with the rank of Senior Member. He is also a Member of ASCE. Wayne was awarded his Bachelor of Science degree in Electrical Engineering from the University of Connecticut in 1977. His professional work has been mostly in power system planning and engineering. He has had a long-term interest in physics and astrophysics.

Poster **Matthew R. Fox (Physics Monastery)**

Matthew R. Fox originates from Lowell, Massachusetts and has always enjoyed building things; be it with Lincoln Logs or LEGOs, he has always been fascinated by how things fit together. Taking a highly circuitous route here through studying business (taking about a week and a half of modern physics in college) and going into the corporate American grind for a decade. Then after becoming tired of the greater political sphere he found himself drawn back into the realm of science. Following a series of unlikely events during a time of plague he finds himself as a monk at the Physics Monastery.

Poster **Gui Furne-Gouveia (Unaffiliated)**

Gui Furne-Gouveia did not pursue a career in Physics or Astrophysics. Yet since his graduate studies in Civil Engineering, he has been fascinated by the great theories of Physics, both impressed and perplexed, unable to help but think that something was wrong with these theories.

But theories are judged by their effectiveness in producing accurate figures. They therefore have some truth at their heart. How could he reconcile these theories with each other and with himself?

His main interests are Physics, Astrophysics, Evolution, Geology, History, and the History of Science.

Poster Neal Graneau (Eliquigen)

Neal Graneau (Fellow Inst. of Physics) (B.Sc. 1986 physics, King's College, London University) (M.Sc. 1987, D.Phil. 1992 plasma physics, University of Oxford) has led various research projects from the development of novel pulsed power transformers to renewable electricity generation with high current density water arc explosions. He now develops high current pulsed power machines for dynamic material properties research. A continuous career thread has been the historical, theoretical, and experimental exploration into the fundamental laws and applications of electromagnetic force. This research feeds into a parallel interest in the philosophical understanding of matter interaction and the cause of inertia.

Poster Michael Gunning (Unaffiliated)

Michael Gunning was born in Ireland in 1969 and graduated from Trinity College Dublin in 1990 with an Honours Degree in Physics and Chemistry. He has worked for the majority of the time since then in the Information and Communications Technology sector. He left the sector in 2021 which has afforded him more time to contemplate the fundamental unanswered questions in Physics and for the last two years has been working on a theory to understand the origins of many of the Constants of Nature.

Poster Chris Lehto (Lehto Files)

Christopher Nash Lehto is a retired U.S. Air Force Lieutenant Colonel and former F-16 fighter pilot with a B.S. in Materials Science from the United States Air Force Academy and an M.S. in Aeronautical Science from Embry-Riddle Aeronautical University. Now based in Portugal, he investigates unidentified aerial phenomena, alternative cosmology, and fractal life theory through his YouTube channel "Lehto Files" (114K subscribers) and podcast. He has flown combat missions, directed NATO fighter-pilot training, and managed multimillion-dollar simulator programs. His forthcoming book *The Cosmic Organism: Fractal Life, Consciousness, and the Living Universe* synthesizes this research for a general audience.

Poster Alan T. Kelly (Unaffiliated)

Alan T. Kelly is an independent researcher exploring potential variation in the fundamental constants of nature - most notably G . His broader aim is to revisit foundational questions in physics and cosmology from a natural-philosophy perspective, distilling each concept to its core and setting aside inherited assumptions. By combining first-principles reasoning with modern computing, he seeks to offer fresh perspectives on long-standing problems and demonstrate how innovative ideas can arise outside traditional academic paths.

- Poster Howard A. Landman (Unaffiliated)
 Howard A. Landman is a retired mathematician, engineer, scientist, and sometimes artist and poet living in Fort Collins, Colorado. He was a co-designer of several major integrated circuits, including the Berkeley RISC I (first RISC microprocessor), HaL SPARC64 (first 64-bit SPARC), and the Emotion Engine chip for the Sony PlayStation 2 (first commercial 128-bit microprocessor). These days he is also an amateur physicist interested in foundational questions, and trying to get a 47-year-old theory of electromagnetic time dilation finally tested.
- Poster Zarrin Leff (Twentynine Palms Astronomy Club/Joshua Tree Excursions)
 Zarrin Leff began studying astronomy as an adult, in earnest in 2022. He has worked primarily in sustainable agriculture and as a naturalist interpretive tour guide, with no formal training in astronomy. He sees this lack of formal training in astronomy as an advantage: a lack of overeducation and indoctrination into a belief system which he thinks is largely wrong. The Astronomy 101 textbook of 100 years from now will look nothing like those of today. He thinks the two biggest problems in astronomy are the gaseous plasma Sun model, and the heliocentric solar system/Euclidean model.
- Poster Sam Mackrill (Unaffiliated) presenting Ray Fleming (Deceased)
 In Ray Fleming's book *The Zero-Point Universe* (2012, 2020), the author is presented as follows: "Ray Fleming is a physicist who recognized in his undergraduate years that the mainstream physics model leaves many of the most basic questions unanswered while other theories contradict each other or even more basic laws of physics. That being the case it was too risky to pursue a career in academia where one has to be indoctrinated into the standard model and eventually lose the ability to think of anything else, so Ray chose to pursue a career in industry while conducting physics research as a pastime. Ray's career began as a civilian working in the US Navy nuclear power program, followed by more than a decade testing and designing X-Ray Fluorescence (XRF) analyzers used for routine elemental analysis. In the last decade Ray has worked as a health physicist for the State of Texas eventually managing radioactive material licensing for the state. In 1990 as a new employee of a XRF analyzer manufacturer some coworkers introduced Ray to some papers by Dr. Hal Puthoff that attempted to show basic physics phenomena as the result of zero-point energy, the vacuum fluctuations that inhabit all of space. Ray knew instantly that zero-point energy was the answer as it was the only thing that is found everywhere in space, the only thing that could be the medium for all force transmission. So began decades of exploration into determining how zero-point vacuum fluctuations interact in each fundamental area of physics." Ray later retired to the Philippines where he could dedicate more time to his studies. Tragically Ray died in early 2024.
 In honour of his life-work, Sam Mackrill will present Ray's theory behind The Zero-Point Universe as a True Believer (in reference to Eric Hoffer's *The True Believer: Thoughts on the Nature of Mass Movements*). Sam is an engineer and will defend robustly his claim that engineering serves as the ultimate proving ground for scientific principles.

- Poster Jack D. Neefus (Unaffiliated)
 Jack D. Neefus lives in Baltimore, Maryland. He is retired from Verizon / Bell Atlantic after a career in finance, product management, IT, and large accounts. He has degrees from the University of Maryland (MBA) and Davidson College (Psychology).
- Poster Artur Novais (Universidade Estadual de Santa Cruz)
 Artur Novais is an associate researcher at the laboratory of theoretical and observational Astrophysics at the University of Santa Cruz, Brazil. Artur's research focus upon new frontiers in Cosmology and Dark Matter. He holds a bachelor's degree in chemical engineering from the Federal University of Bahia, including an exchange year at the University of Surrey – UK. Artur works as a senior manufacturing manager at the Dow Chemical Company. In 2023, he obtained his master's degree in Astrophysics and his major publications are *Lorentzian Correction for the Evolution of the CMB Temperature, Astrophysics 67, 348–363 (2024)* and *The Galactic Pizza: Flat Rotation Curves in the Context of Cosmological Time-Energy Coupling, Galaxies 2025, 13, 51*.
- Poster Thad Roberts (Physics Monastery)
 Thad Roberts is a physicist and philosopher of science, formerly with NASA. His research explores the idea that Nature's constants are structural consequences of a deeper geometric order. Working from the Physics Monastery, he has developed a unifying framework in which all 288 physical constants arise from the topology of the hyperbolic figure eight knot. He is the author of *Einstein's Intuition* and other works exploring the intersection of geometry, measurement, and meaning.
- Poster Sebastian Schepis (University of Connecticut)
 Sebastian Schepis is a computer scientist, engineer, and theorist whose work explores the deep structure of reality through the unification of number theory, quantum mechanics, consciousness, and information. He is the creator of the Prime Resonance Framework, a model that positions prime numbers as the fundamental eigenstates of spacetime and treats consciousness not as an emergent artifact but as the primordial substrate from which physical laws arise. Sebastian's research integrates gravitational wave data, pulsar timing arrays, symbolic computation, and entropy-driven collapse dynamics into a coherent theoretical framework that challenges conventional paradigms in physics and cognitive science.

Attendees

- Attendee Neil Creamer (Unaffiliated)
 Neil obtained a BSc in Chemistry in 1999 and a PhD in 2003, following 20 years working in the UK National Health Service as a microbiologist. He researched bionanotechnology in the Applied Microbiology group at The University of Birmingham until 2013 and is now an independent researcher and

author. His interests are the philosophy and history of science, and metascience, the scientific study of the scientific process itself.

Attendee **Tim Dodge (NCC Fab Lab / Dent Design Hardware)**

Tim Dodge is an associate professor of 3D printing and 3D CAD and the president of Dent Design Hardware, with an undergrad from Moravian college and degrees in mathematics, philosophy, computer science and engineering from FAU Erlangen-Nuremberg. Utilizing Zcorp, Stratasys and Rep-Rap/derivatives, his track record counts over 10,000 3D prints at a 95% hit rate. He designed over 500 sand and diecast tools, which he developed for rapid manufacturing and rapid tooling. His past accomplishments further include the development of the haptic glove control as a core member of the NCC Fab Lab robotics team for the TOBOR 10' dinosaur robot, the most medaled entrant in Makerfaire history, in addition to successfully wrestling the TOBOR robot to the ground on several occasions. His green fingers earned him the EPA/DEP (USA) Small Business Environmental National Stewardship Award in 2021. More recently, he joined the Monroe Institute Consciousness Studies and considers himself a student of Quantized Inertia and Weber Electrodynamics, for immanent applications in levitating skateboards.

Attendee **Anjan Katta (Daylight Computer)**

Founder of Daylight Computer (daylightcomputer.com) - building kindle on steroids - a 60fps epaper tablet & stylus that's awesome for reading papers, docs, pdfs, blogs, and books. The goal is to truly make computers actually bicycles for the mind. Passionate about exploring metaphysics, Exo-Studies, spiritual experiences, and learning widely!

Attendee **Alona (Elena) Litovinskaia (Unaffiliated)**

Alona Litovinskaia is an interdisciplinary researcher and technologist focusing on quantum information science, nonlocal communication, and novel device architectures. Her recent work centers on ambient, infrastructure-free quantum teleportation protocols, integrating concepts from octonionic geometry, topological materials, and signal modulation theory. She leads the QGate initiative, developing a chip-scale quantum modem designed for secure, correlation-based communication. Alona is passionate about bridging fundamental physics with practical engineering and has been actively involved in creating frameworks for post-internet communication networks.

Attendee **Mana MacDougall (Unaffiliated)**

Mana MacDougall is a Persian visual artist and filmmaker. She does not bring a scientific theory, but a story about the origins of life, in a Sumerian fashion. They designed the first civilization of Mesopotamia and the first human story ever documented. Before any Adam and Eve, Isis and Osiris, Jesus and Mary, Buddha and Mohammad, or any other cult, or religion. They called themselves Anunnaki and believed that they were the last surviving members of an extra-terrestrial nation who landed on earth first in Mesopotamia and brought their advanced knowledge and technology with them and taught them to their hominid counterparts. They initiated a language and writing system and depicted their story in clay tablets and carved stones. You can follow Mana's story at manamacdougall.com

- Attendee Lukáš Neterda (Unaffiliated)
Lukáš Neterda is a cofounder of several IT start-ups and right now responsible for AI development at MPS friends, which has been rebranded as AI friends. He has a background in math, as well as a little bit of material science from when he was working at www.respilon.com.
- Attendee John Plaice (Unaffiliated)
John Plaice is a former computer scientist and software engineer, having worked both in academia and industry. He is now writing about the history of science, through his blog:
Fiat Lux: Thoughts on the History of Science (<https://johnplaice.substack.com>)
John likes to focus on historical debates, and finds of particular interest the role of electricity in the cosmos, as well as the ideas of an infinite universe and of instantaneous action-at-a-distance. He has recently started blogs in French and Spanish, in which appear translations of some of his writings:
Fiat Lux en français (<https://fiatluxfr.substack.com>)
Fiat Lux en español (<https://fiatluxes.substack.com>)
He can be reached at johnplaice@protonmail.com.
- Attendee John Russell (Unaffiliated)
John Russell holds an MSc in Astrophysics from the University of Guelph, where he specialized in computational modeling and simulation of protoplanetary disk formation. With a strong foundation in scientific problem-solving, he transitioned into professional software development, building robust, user-focused systems across diverse industries. With experience leading development teams in both tech startups and the space sector, he now runs a technical consulting business focused on scientific and specialized applications that benefit from a startup mindset.
- Attendee Peter Sykes (Unaffiliated)
Long term follower of Electric Universe. Interested in wider topics of cosmology, physics and computing.
- Attendee Ben Watson (Unaffiliated)
Ben Watson was born in 1956 and studied history and English literature at Cambridge University. His mother got him reading R. G. Collingwood at an early age, which led to an interest in in the writings of Giordano Bruno, Frederick Engels and Alfred North Whitehead. He has written extensively about music, including books on Frank Zappa and Derek Bailey, and presents two weekly radio shows in London. His partner is the writer Esther Leslie with whom he's had two children, Iris (born 2005) and Mordecai (born 2008).
- Attendee Daniel E. Whitaker (Physics Monastery)
A curious person.

DemystiCon 2025 Full Program

=====**Thursday, June 12, 2025**=====

===== **A New Cosmological Beginning** =====

Registration & Welcoming Reception (15:00 – 17:00)

Refreshments & Snacks (15:30 – 16:00)

Opening Remarks (15:50 – 16:00)

15:50 – 15:55

Welcoming Speech from the Organizing Committee

- Anastasia Bendebury and Michael Shilo Delay (DemystifySci)

15:55 – 16:00

Welcoming Speech from the Publication Committee

- Patrick Vanraes (University of Antwerp)

Event **Cosmological Speed Friending** (16:00 – 17:00)

Session A **Invited Talks** (17:00 – 19:00)

17:00 – 18:00

[A-1] The challenge of doing fundamental physics

- Alexander Unzicker (Pestalozzi-Gymnasium München / The Machian)

18:00 – 19:00

[A-2] **[Keynote]** Time to abandon the Big Bang/Expansion Hypothesis

- Eric Lerner (LPPFusion, Inc.)

----- Dinner Break (19:00 – 21:00) -----

===== Friday, June 13, 2025 =====
===== Cosmic Microwave Background =====

Session B Invited Talks (9:00 – 13:00)

9:00 – 10:00

- [B-1] The blackbody & the ion: a materials science approach to the stars
- Michael Shilo Delay (Southern Oregon University / DemystifySci)

10:00 – 10:30

- [B-2] Cold fusion in a liquid Sun – Exploring the theoretical possibilities
- Patrick Vanraes (University of Antwerp)

10:30 – 11:00

- [B-3] Earth's oceans as the source of the Cosmic Microwave Background – the biggest threat
to standard cosmology
- Patrick Vanraes (University of Antwerp)

11:00 – 12:00

- [B-4] Solving the Hubble tension with a large local void
- Indranil Banik (University of Portsmouth)

12:00 – 13:00

- [B-5] The Cosmic Microwave Background radiation with a temperature of 2.75 Kelvin
is a proof against the Big Bang, since it was predicted earlier and better
by an infinite universe without expansion, than the predictions based on the Big Bang
- Andre Koch Torres Assis (University of Campinas)

----- Lunch Break (13:00 – 14:00) -----

Poster Session P1 (14:00 – 17:00)

- [P-1] A Surprising Way to Calculate the Proton/Electron Mass Ratio
 - Gui Furne-Gouveia (Unaffiliated)

- [P-3] The Constants of Nature
 - Thad Roberts (Physics Monastery)

- [P-5] Cosmic Redshift Elegantly Explained by Minkowski Space-Time and General Relativity
 - Wayne H. Coste (Unaffiliated)

- [P-7] Cosmology begins on the lab bench
 - Neal Graneau (Eliquisgen)

- [P-9] The ZerØ-Point Universe
 - Sam Mackrill (Unaffiliated)

- [P-11] A new solar system model, the Tychos
 - Zarrin Leff (Twentynine Palms Astronomy Club/Joshua Tree Excursions)

- [P-13] The Exochronous Universe: a timeless metric as a possible alternative to dark matter
 - Robin Booth (University of Sussex)

- [P-15] No Big Bang: Redshift from fundamental physics
 - Alan T. Kelly (Unaffiliated)

- [P-17] The cosmic web can be explained by gradual, diffuse, electrically polarized creation
 - Jack D. Neefus (Unaffiliated)

Panel B Evening Panel Discussion (17:00 – 19:00)

What is the nature of the CMB?

- Gareth Samuel
- Indranil Banik
- Patrick Vanraes
- Andre Koch Torres Assis

----- Dinner Break (19:30 – 21:30) -----

===== Saturday, June 14, 2025 =====
===== Redshift & Distant Galaxies =====

Session C Invited Talks (9:00 – 13:00)

9:00 – 10:00

- [C-1] Applying Einstein’s best idea to cosmology: variable speed of light
- Alexander Unzicker (Pestalozzi-Gymnasium München / The Machian)

10:00 – 11:00

- [C-2] The good and the ‘not so good’ aspects of standard cosmology: a review
- C. S. Unnikrishnan (Defence Institute of Advanced Technology)

11:00 – 12:00

- [C-3] Problems of the Standard Model in Cosmology
- Martín López-Corredoira (Instituto de Astrofísica de Canarias)

12:00 – 13:00

- [C-4] The high redshift, mass, and collision velocity of the El Gordo galaxy cluster collision contradicts standard cosmology
- Indranil Banik (University of Portsmouth)

----- Lunch Break (13:00 – 14:30) -----

Event Paradigm Drift – DemystiCon 2025 edition (14:30 – 16:30)

<https://demystifysci.com/paradigm-drift-show>

Panel C Evening Panel Discussion (17:00 – 19:00)

How do we need to interpret redshifts and early galaxies?

- Alexander Unzicker
- C.S. Unnikrisnan
- Martín López-Corredoira
- Eric Lerner

----- Dinner Break (19:00 – 21:00) -----

===== Sunday, June 15, 2025 =====
===== Alternative Cosmologies =====

Session D Invited Talks (9:00 – 13:00)

9:00 – 10:00

- [D-1] Quantised inertia: a cosmology that is directly testable & useful
- Mike McCulloch (University of Plymouth)

10:00 – 11:00

- [D-2] Cosmic Evolution with no Big Bang
- Eric Lerner (LPPFusion, Inc.)

11:00 – 12:00

- [D-3] Unraveling the Big Bang: why finding flaws isn't enough to overturn
a cosmological paradigm
- Gareth Samuel (See the Pattern)

12:00 – 13:00

- [D-4] The gravity of the universe and the physics of dynamics and relativity
- C. S. Unnikrishnan (Defense Institute of Advanced Technology)

----- Lunch Break (13:00 – 14:00) -----

Poster Session P2 (14:00 – 17:00)

- [P-2] The constants of nature, G , h , e , m_e , m_p , m_n , μ_e , μ_p and μ_n , explained by
reinterpreting μ_0 and ϵ_0
- Michael Gunning (Unaffiliated)

- [P-4] A Revolutionary New Theory of Light
- Gary Barham (The Alchemist Studio)

- [P-6] A physical mechanism for dark energy
- Matthew R. Fox (Physics Monastery)

- [P-8] Quantum Time Dilation as a Key to Unified Theories
- Howard A. Landman (Unaffiliated)

- [P-10] Problems with the bedrock of astronomical theory—the heliocentric solar system model and the gaseous sun—show the need for embracing uncertainty and observations in favor of jumping to theories
 - Zarrin Leff (Twentynine Palms Astronomy Club/Joshua Tree Excursions)
- [P-12] Prime Resonance Across Astrophysical Systems: A Universal Law of Gravitational and Electromagnetic Dynamics
 - Sebastian Schepis (University of Connecticut)
- [P-14] The Jeans Contraction: the origins of redshift in a static universe
 - Robin Booth (University of Sussex)
- [P-16] The Fractal Universe: How Patterns Repeat from Cells to Galaxies
 - Chris Lehto (Lehto Files)
- [P-18] The galactic pizza: flat rotation curves in the context of cosmological time-energy coupling
 - Artur Novais (Universidade Estadual de Santa Cruz)

Panel D Evening Panel Discussion (17:00 – 19:00)

Do we need a new cosmology or to repair the old one?

- Mike McCulloch
- Gareth Samuel
- Andre Koch Torres Assis
- Martín López-Corredoira

----- Dinner Break (19:00 – 21:00) -----

===== Monday, June 16, 2025 =====
===== Shifting the Paradigm =====

Session E Invited Talks (9:00 – 10:30)

9:00 – 10:00

- [E-1] **[Keynote]** The snowball effect as a sociological factor in the creation of alternative cosmologies
- Martín López-Corredoira (Instituto de Astrofísica de Canarias)

10:00 – 10:30

- [E-2] Paving the Roadmap for non-standard astrophysics and cosmology
- Patrick Vanraes (University of Antwerp)

Event Paving the Roadmap Think Tank Workshop (10:30 – 12:00)

Closing Remarks (12:00 – 12:10)

12:00 – 12:05

- Goodbye Speech from the Publication Committee
- Patrick Vanraes (University of Antwerp)

12:05 – 12:10

- Goodbye Speech from the Organizing Committee
- Anastasia Bendebury and Michael Shilo DeLay (DemystifySci)

Session A

A New Cosmological Beginning

The challenge of doing fundamental physics

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In contemporary discussions, there is no shortage of alternative ideas for Theories of Everything (TOEs), unifications, and the like, but there lacks an objective metric to gauge progress. Historical evidence suggests that such progress has consistently been associated with the explanation of natural constants [1]. Consequently, these quantities, often overlooked or dismissed by modern theories, should be central to our focus when seeking revolutionary insights. In this talk, I propose which constants should be elucidated; the significant challenges involved will be highlighted [2].

References

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Time to abandon the Big Bang/Expansion hypothesis

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The test of scientific validity is that a hypothesis makes predictions that are confirmed by subsequent observations. But the Big Bang/Expanding Universe hypothesis has been repeatedly invalidated by many separate data sets. Instead of abandoning the hypothesis as invalid, most cosmologists have abandoned instead the scientific method, “explaining” observations already made with new tweaks in the hypothesis, such as dark energy and dark matter. This is the Ptolemaic, not the scientific method.

Today, the expansion hypothesis is directly contradicted by galaxy surface brightness and size data [1]. Expansion is also contradicted by the enormous age of the largest-scale structures such as the Big Arc and Big Ring [2], and by too-great ages of stars, globular clusters and galaxies. A hot, dense (Big Bang) stage in cosmic evolution is contradicted by the abundance of helium and lithium and by the absence of any evidence of baryon number non-conservation (unequal production of protons and antiprotons) [3].

Many other data sets, including those showing the non-existence of dark matter, the non-randomness of the CMB, and the value of the Hubble constant, contradict the “concordance” LCDM version of the Big Bang hypothesis. Only the deuterium abundance is still in accord with Big Bang predictions.

In contrast, there are no contradictions for the hypothesis of non-expansion, as I will detail in my presentation on Cosmic Evolution.

Cosmologists are starting to abandon LCDM. Instead, they should abandon the entire Big Bang expansion hypothesis.

References

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Session B

Cosmic Microwave Background

The blackbody & the ion: a materials science approach to the stars

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Astrophysical sciences form the basis of myriad fields of philosophy and engineering, including cosmological science and nuclear fusion. Many of these disciplines have failed to reach their promise, instead delivering a cosmos of darkness rather than light. Taming the power of the stars ever remains a distant hope for humanity, barely inching forward with each generation. Plasma is the critical concept at the heart of stellar physics, and yet the term is vague, often used inconsistently, and as a result, basic laws of radiation and electrodynamics are frequently misapplied. We propose that the path forward requires a material science approach to fundamental atomics, where plasma can be best understood by assigning plausible architecture to the atoms and then applying this model to electromagnetism, ionization, and thermal radiation. Using a material model of the atom we explain why and how different plasmas present in stars generate their diverse spectral features, and ultimately reveal a general framework for atomics that we believe might accelerate humanity's access to power of the stars while also paving the way toward a more comprehensible and fruitful cosmological science.

Cold fusion in a liquid Sun – Exploring the theoretical possibilities

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In the standard solar model, energy generation is dominated by nuclear fusion reactions between protons in the Sun's gaseous core, at a density six orders of magnitude higher than hydrogen at standard conditions. For this process to occur at a sufficient rate, temperatures over ten million Kelvin are required, to overcome the Coulomb barrier between the protons. Similar conditions are not available in the liquid metallic hydrogen model of the Sun, as developed by Pierre-Marie Robitaille, in which densities are assumed to be more uniform at markedly lower temperatures [1]. Different mechanisms are therefore required to explain the presence of nuclear fusion reactions in such a condensed state. Robitaille, for instance, proposed lattice confinement of protons, lattice vibrations, Debye shielding by conduction electrons, internal pressure and the enormous kinetic energy in solar convection currents as possible contributors to solar fusion reactions [2].

In the present talk, I will explore the theoretical possibilities of cold fusion in a liquid Sun. For this purpose, I will combine Robitaille's solar model with the recent theoretical work by Metzler et al. on cold fusion [3], as well as the multi-plasma model that I developed to describe electronically and vibrationally excited matter [4]. This combination reveals the possibility of defect- and quasiparticle-assisted fusion reactions in a condensed environment at strongly reduced temperatures, relative to the gaseous solar model. In particular, electronic plasmons are expected to enable local Debye shielding enhancement, decreasing the Coulomb barriers on a time- and space-dependent basis. Moreover, electronic excitation of a metallic material can locally cause an ultrafast lattice contraction due to phonon hardening [5], which may further facilitate fusion reactions on a local level.

Such cold fusion mechanisms are not only relevant for condensed solar and stellar models, they also provide promising alternative pathways to establish controllable fusion reactions in the laboratory, in condensed media as opposed to conventional fusion reactors. In short, they predict that if one can manipulate the electronic energy in the condensed medium locally and at ultrafast time scales (picoseconds or less), low-temperature fusion becomes more likely. The same mechanisms may also underlie neutron generation in lightning in the presence of ice particles [6], indicating intense and/or ultrafast electrical current pulses as attractive candidates to generate cold fusion.

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B-2

Earth's oceans as the source of the Cosmic Microwave Background – The biggest threat to standard cosmology

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Standard cosmology in its current form is heavily based on the Big Bang theory, which on its turn heavily relies on the observation of the Cosmic Microwave Background (CMB). Proponents of the Big Bang frequently present the CMB as “solid evidence” and “strong support” for their theory [1-2]. In the present talk, I will argue instead why the CMB is, ironically, standard cosmology's weakest link. My argumentation may be understood as a selective review and restructuring of Pierre-Marie Robitaille's work on the CMB (e.g. [3]), tailored to the question: where does the CMB come from? Based on discussions on social media, I will additionally indicate a few common misconceptions about Robitaille's work and propose a strategy to overcome them in future debates.

The most widespread misconception is the confusion between the CMB's monopole and the multipoles. Not making this distinction may result in the failure to recognize that these microwave signals are measured by different instruments. Robitaille's hypothesis that the CMB comes from Earth's oceans refers exclusively to the monopole, whereas most criticism on this idea assumes the opposite. In order to mitigate this persistent misunderstanding, I recommend introducing a new terminology to more easily distinguish between the CMB signals: Blackbody Microwave Background (BMB) for the monopole versus Anisotropic Microwave Background (AMB) for the multipoles.

A second misconception seems to be that the detection of AMB at a distant location from Earth would suffice as evidence for the Big Bang theory. This is incorrect, because the latter requires a thermal radiation background. Hence, the main debate needs to focus on the BMB. As a third prevalent misconception, it is often assumed that BMB cannot originate from the oceans, because it was measured by the FIRAS detector of the COBE satellite, which was pointed away from the Earth. This assumption ignores the possibility of microwave diffraction or in-flight leakage into FIRAS, which was neither measured or appropriately computed, as pointed out in detail by Robitaille [3].

In short, Robitaille's work on the CMB reveals a lack of solid experimental evidence that the BMB would come from outer space. Strong arguments to the contrary remain absent in the debate for now. Instead, the absence of the BMB in Herouni's telescope measurements [4] have presented themselves as alarming counterevidence against the Big Bang. This demands further investigations into the predictions by Robitaille that the Big Bang theory is incorrect and the BMB originates from the oceans.

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Solving the Hubble tension with a large local void

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Cosmology is currently in a crisis known as the Hubble tension, the observation that redshift increases with distance about 10% faster than expected in the Λ CDM standard cosmological paradigm with parameters calibrated to fit the CMB anisotropies. A promising explanation for this is that we live near the centre of a large local underdensity or void. This is suggested by observations of source number counts across the whole electromagnetic spectrum, with near-infrared results implying that the density is about 20% below average out to 300 Mpc across 90% of the sky and most of the galaxy luminosity function [1]. Outflows from this “KBC void” can induce enough extra redshift to plausibly solve the Hubble tension [2]. I will discuss various tests of this proposal. At low redshift, the bulk flow of galaxies traces the average velocity of matter within a sphere centred on our location. The observed bulk flow curve is in good agreement with the void model predictions [3]. Looking further out, the model is supported by the declining trend with redshift of the recovered present expansion rate H_0 [4]. Moreover, baryon acoustic oscillation (BAO) datasets show a deviation from Λ CDM expectations. I will explain how the BAO observables would be affected by a local void. I will then present BAO results compiled over the last twenty years. These results fit slightly better if the local void is included, thanks to good agreement with Λ CDM at high redshift but a persistent anomaly that appears at lower redshift [5].

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The Cosmic Microwave Background radiation with a temperature of 2.75 Kelvin is a proof against the Big Bang, since it was predicted earlier and better by an infinite universe without expansion, than the predictions based on the Big Bang

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Most textbooks claim that the cosmic microwave background radiation of 2.75 K is a proof of the Big Bang as it had been predicted before its discovery by Penzias and Wilson in 1965. Contrary to this statement, we show that the Big Bang predicted wrong and increasing temperatures, in this order: (a) In 1948, Alpher and Herman arrived at $T = 5$ K. (b) In 1949, they obtained $T > 5$ K. (c) Gamow, in 1953, arrived at 7 K. (d) Then Gamow finally in 1961, predicted it as 50 K. Moreover, scientists working with an infinite universe without expansion predicted this temperature earlier and better than the predictions of the Big Bang: (a) In 1896, the Nobel prize winner C. E. Guillaume obtained 5.6 K for the temperature of space. (b) In 1926, A. Eddington obtained 3.18 K. (c) In 1933, E. Regener, working with cosmic rays obtained a temperature of intergalactic space of 2.8 K. (d) The Nobel prize winner W. Nernst, working explicitly with an Universe in a stationary space and with a cosmological redshift not due to a Doppler effect, arrived at 0.75 K. (e) A. McKellar and Herberg in 1941 arrived at 2.3 K. (f) E. Finlay-Freundlich proposed in 1953-1954 a tired light mechanism to explain the redshift of solar lines and when he applied his model to the cosmological redshift obtained $1.9 \text{ K} < T < 6.0 \text{ K}$. (g) In 1954, the Nobel prize Max Born predicted that Finlay-Freundlich's tired light model was linked to radio-astronomy. Only 11 years later Penzias and Wilson discovered the CMBR with temperature of 3.1 K utilizing a horn antenna built to study radio waves! In conclusion, the CMBR is a proof against the Big Bang, since it was predicted earlier and better by an infinite universe without expansion, than the predictions based on the Big Bang.

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Session C

Redshift & Distant Galaxies

Applying Einstein's best idea to cosmology: variable speed of light

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Variable speed of light, Einstein's initial concept when developing general relativity between 1907 and 1911, represents an alternative formulation to the latter [1,2] but is radically different from current cosmological models. It offers a variety of intriguing explanations for some of the most fundamental issues, extending beyond cosmology itself—calculating the gravitational constant's value, providing a rationale for cosmological redshift, and unifying inertia and gravity in line with Mach's principle, and even Dirac's hypotheses [3]. While this approach aligns with the endeavors of the brightest minds such as Einstein, Schrödinger, Dirac, Mach, Sciama, and Dicke, significant challenges remain in the context of variable scales.

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The good and the ‘not so good’ aspects of standard cosmology: a review

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The standard model of cosmology is nearly as respected at present as the standard model of particle physics. It is “standard” in the sense of a consensus evolved over several decades of observations and theoretical interpretations. I will review the major ideas evolved in the formulation of a standard model, placing them in the context of observational evidence that every model of the Universe must respect. Then I will point to the uncomfortable features that we accept without sufficient understanding or evidence, and mention some major alternate paradigms that have been explored. The goal of my review is to motivate a discussion to see whether there are any major inconsistencies, especially of a conceptual nature, in the making of the standard model of cosmology. Some topics that will be specifically mentioned are ‘quantum vacuum and inflation’, ‘redshifts, the expansion of space, and energy conservation’, ‘infinite or finite Universe’, ‘Milne’s explosion cosmology, his cosmological principle, and the role of gravity in the dynamics of the Universe’.

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Problems of the standard model in cosmology

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Cosmological observations find explanations within the standard Lambda-CDM model, although many times after a number of ad hoc corrections. Nevertheless, the expression ‘crisis in cosmology’ stubbornly reverberates in the scientific literature [1,2]: the higher the precision with which the standard cosmological model tries to fit the data, the greater the number of tensions that arise. Moreover, there are alternative explanations for most of the observations. There are anomalies on galactic to Gpc scales (large-scale structure) including some examples of 5-sigma tensions, on CMBR, nucleosynthesis, tests of expansion, CP violation, inflation and other topics. The general conclusion is that cosmological hypotheses should be very cautiously proposed and even more cautiously received.

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The high redshift, mass, and collision velocity of the El Gordo galaxy cluster collision contradicts standard cosmology

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The El Gordo galaxy clusters are a massive interacting pair observed at redshift 0.87 [1]. Hydrodynamical simulations of the collision in a non-cosmological context require a collision velocity of at least 2500 km/s to match observations. A rapid collision of such massive clusters is very unlikely in the Λ CDM standard cosmological paradigm when the universe was about half its current age. In this talk, I will discuss how we quantified the likelihood of observing a cluster pair similar to El Gordo. Analyses in the literature typically treat El Gordo as just one object, but finding two massive clusters within striking distance is far less likely. We quantify this issue in detail, finding the distribution in our past lightcone of redshift and total mass for galaxy cluster pairs moving together at supersonic velocities. These pairs are essentially lower mass analogues to El Gordo, allowing us to build up the statistics and extrapolate to its very high mass [2]. We apply this lightcone tomography technique to El Gordo using a weak lensing measurement of its total mass ($2 \times 10^{15} M_{\odot}$) accurate to 10% [3]. The results show that El Gordo is incompatible with Λ CDM at over 5σ confidence for any plausible collision velocity allowed by hydrodynamical simulations, thus ruling out Λ CDM as a viable theory of nature at >99.9999% confidence [4]. I argue that structure formation on large scales was more efficient than predicted in this paradigm, given density fluctuations on the relevant scales are constrained using the observed cosmic microwave background anisotropies.

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Session D

Alternative Cosmologies

Quantised inertia: a cosmology that is directly testable & useful

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The physics developed in the early 20th century was an advance, but set a precedent for adding untestable elements such as curved space-time. Recently, new observations from deep space: galaxy clusters [1], galaxies [2] and wide binaries [3] have falsified general relativity, but it is difficult to challenge because curved space-time is not directly testable and complex fixes such as dark matter cannot be exhaustively falsified. For real physics, a theory must be falsifiable in the laboratory, where conditions can be carefully controlled to prove that no other options are possible. A new cosmology called quantised inertia (QI) was suggested by McCulloch [4-6]. Instead of attributing motion to assumed laws, it attributes motion to the push from gradients in the quantum vacuum (Unruh radiation) caused by damping from Rindler horizons (causing inertia) or matter (causing gravity). The damping of that radiation also by the cosmic horizon predicts a new modification to inertia that predicts the rotation of galaxy clusters, galaxies and wide binaries without adjustment [7]. QI only uses testable elements (Unruh radiation was recently seen by Lynch *et al.* [8]) and it can be tested simply in a laboratory. To do that, it is necessary to look at a system where the acceleration is so high that the Unruh radiation becomes short enough to be damped by man-made metal structures and then anomalous motion is predicted to occur [5, 9]. Becker and Bhatt [10] proposed the use of highly charged capacitors and in five laboratories anomalous capacitor thrust has been seen as predicted by QI [11]. QI's testability also means that it is useful, offering quantum thrust and new sources of energy [11]. It is a major shift in physics, deviating subtly from Newton's laws, eliminating the need for G, & bringing the concept of information into physics.

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Cosmic evolution with no Big Bang

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The Big Bang hypothesis is falling apart, washed away by the flood of data from JWST and other telescopes. But if the Big Bang never happened, what did? For over forty years, the contrary hypothesis, that there was no Big Bang and is no expansion, has made correct predictions of subsequent observations, based only on lab-verified physical phenomena and theories. I summarize here these observations, including some very recent ones.

A combination of gravity and electromagnetic plasma processes—particularly the filamentation instability—has led over trillions of years to the formation of the observed hierarchy of large-scale structures, superclusters and clusters of galaxies, galaxies, stars and planets [1]. The quantitative description of galaxy formation shows that young galaxies produce helium, lithium and deuterium in the observed quantities, as well beryllium and boron. The energy produced by converting hydrogen into helium powers the CMB and filaments generated in quasars and AGN scatter and thermalize the radiation [2].

Understanding the processes that generated the cosmos that we now see helps us to harness these processes here on earth—especially to develop cheap, clean, safe and unlimited fusion energy.

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Unraveling the Big Bang: why finding flaws isn't enough to overturn a cosmological paradigm

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The Big Bang model is widely regarded as the foundation of modern cosmology, supported by key observations such as redshift-distance relations, the cosmic microwave background (CMB), and element abundances. However, much of this support relies on inferred data rather than direct measurement, making it difficult to disentangle observational evidence from model-dependent interpretation. This presentation explores the challenges of overturning the Big Bang, emphasizing that inconsistencies alone are insufficient to displace an entrenched paradigm.

First, we examine the fundamental limitations of observational cosmology, where electromagnetic radiation provides only two-dimensional snapshots of a four-dimensional universe. From this limited data, models are constructed using inferred quantities, introducing circular reasoning—where assumptions shape the interpretation of evidence, which then reinforces those same assumptions. Examples include the calibration of redshift with standard candles, the CMB power spectrum fitting, and the introduction of dark energy to explain SN1a dimming.

We then discuss why alternative models, such as Plasma Cosmology, struggle to gain acceptance—not necessarily due to lack of validity, but because data is pre-filtered through Big Bang assumptions. Furthermore, the Big Bang model has remained viable due to its adaptability; anomalies are often resolved by introducing theoretical patches that fix multiple issues at once, making the model difficult to falsify.

Ultimately, we argue that overturning the Big Bang requires more than pointing out inconsistencies—it demands a paradigm shift in how cosmological data is interpreted, requiring a model that explains observations more accurately, with fewer assumptions and greater predictive power.

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The gravity of the universe and the physics of dynamics and relativity

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The standard theory and models of the evolving Universe are based on our theories of dynamics and relativity. The current theories of physics (the theories of relativity and quantum mechanics) were formulated and completed before 1930, well before we acquired reliable knowledge about the factual size of the Universe or about its matter and energy content. This leads to an obvious and serious inconsistency, because the enormous amount of matter and energy in the vast Universe have an equally enormous gravitational effect on everything in this Universe, and in the laboratory, especially on the relativistic dynamics of particles and on the propagation of light. However, these cosmic gravitational effects are not any part of the theories of relativity or quantum mechanics. I will show convincing experimental evidence, on many counts, to prove that the current foundations of dynamics and relativity are flawed and incorrect. I will show that the gravity of the Universe is the single determining factor of dynamics and relativity of particles and light. The laws of dynamics as well as all features of motional relativity are physical consequences of the gravity of the Universe. Clear and impeccable experimental evidence to prove that the genuine one-way relative speed of light is in fact Galilean, and not an invariant constant, is the highlight that demands a drastic revision of the foundations. Then a natural question arises about how the revised foundations based on the gravity of the Universe may affect the theory of the evolving Universe itself. I will try to address some relevant issues, without any speculation.

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Session E

Shifting the Paradigm

The snowball effect as a sociological factor in the creation of alternative cosmologies

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Most cosmologists do not usually work within the framework of alternative cosmologies very different from the standard one because they feel that these are not at present as competitive as the standard model. It is true that they are not so developed, but that is because cosmologists do not work on them. This vicious circle is to a great extent due to a sociological phenomenon known as the "snowball effect" [1,2], also called Matthew effect [3], in which resources are distributed to the most successful theory at a given time; the effect acts as a potential in a field that attracts cosmologists, causing funds, research positions, prestige, telescope time, publication in top journals, citations, conferences, and other resources to be dedicated almost exclusively to standard cosmology.

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Paving the Roadmap for non-standard cosmology and astrophysics

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Non-standard cosmology and non-standard astrophysics may be understood as a cluster of alternatives to the contemporary standard models of cosmology and astrophysics. In this context, a standard model refers to the scientific consensus, i.e. the opinion of the majority of scientists in the corresponding field of study. One may therefore be tempted to see non-standard science as void of consensus and structure, but this is incorrect. Instead, it is better defined as the pluralistic domain in science that welcomes alternatives to the majority's opinion and in which certain levels of like-mindedness and organization can exist. Despite being a minority, proponents of non-standard science can therefore share a similar vision and mission in their research and their philosophy of science.

My present talk serves as an introduction to a think tank workshop at the DemystiCon 2025 conference that aims to define and explore this shared vision and mission in non-standard cosmology and astrophysics, in order to synthesize them into a Roadmap article. First, I explain the concept of a Roadmap and how it can organize a field, by means of its usual purpose, structure and elements. Next, I propose a novel philosophical multi-tier model to chart a non-standard scientific field, in order to structure further discussions on the Roadmap. The model combines the descriptive Kuhnian paradigm concept with Lakatos' research programme configuration, taking into account both sociological and epistemic dimensions. It defines any non-standard scientific field as the challenger of its standard counterpart. The standard paradigm is assumed to be structured in at least three parts:

- The **critical hard core** incorporates foundational assumptions that cannot be rejected or replaced without abandoning the entire paradigm (paradigm rejection).
- The **peripheral hard core** contains other foundational assumptions that may be rejected or replaced in times of crisis to save a part of the paradigm (paradigm reformation).
- The **protective belt** includes auxiliary hypotheses, methodological rules, and theoretical adaptations that can be modified in response to empirical anomalies (paradigm refinement).

Accordingly, the non-standard paradigm challenges the standard one in at least three tiers, for instance: Tier 1 for the critical hard core, Tier 2 for the peripheral hard core and Tier 3 for the protective belt. The higher number of layers relative to Lakatos' research programme model enables a hierarchic picture of the hard core, useful for expressing how critical an assumption is relative to another for the standard paradigm. As a first example for standard cosmology in its current form, special relativity may be considered more critical than general relativity. Similarly, the Big Bang theory and the CMB as relic radiation are more foundational than inflation. It is also necessary to distinguish between the existence of dark matter and dark energy versus dark matter candidates and dark energy mechanisms, as the latter are less controversial. Part of the workshop focuses on how this picture needs to be filled in for non-standard cosmology and non-standard astrophysics.

E-2

Poster Session

Constants of Nature

A Surprising Way to Calculate the Proton/Electron Mass Ratio

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A forgotten physicist, T.N. Lockyer, suggested a calculation of the proton/electron mass ratio giving a result whose first seven significant figures are correct [1]. This calculation uses only physical constants. Pure coincidence? You be the judge.

The strangest thing is that quarks appear nowhere in the suggested structure because it's a layered structure, like Russian dolls.

What's striking is the claim that there's no "cheating." No arbitrary numbers are slipped in to force the result. The constants and their relationships do all the work, and the units balance perfectly, as they must in any legit physical calculation. The calculation's transparency is part of its appeal—you can check the logic yourself and see there's no sleight of hand.

Could this be a clue to a hidden connection between the electron and proton? In physics, the electron's mass comes from its interaction with the Higgs field, while the proton's mass is mostly due to the strong force binding quarks inside it. These are wildly different mechanisms, so a direct link feels like a stretch. Yet, the numbers don't lie—or do they?

You'll find more details in the blog and paper I prepared for this occasion [2-3]. It doesn't contain the complete theory behind this calculation, as it would require word-for-word copying of his entire theory published during his lifetime, and there are probably copyright issues to be respected. But there is his program translated into javascript that you can use for your checks, and a brief summary of his theory.

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The constants of nature, G , h , e , m_e , m_p , m_n , μ_e , μ_p and μ_n , explained by reinterpreting μ_0 and ϵ_0

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The Standard Model of Particle Physics is held up as one of the most successful theories in physics, but it is littered with dubious renormalised infinities, multiple fundamental particles and nothing at all about gravity.

For over seventy years Physics has failed to unify General Relativity and Quantum Mechanics because in my view they are both only mathematical constructs and incorrect interpretations of reality and are thus incapable of unification.

In this paper I revive the idea of the aether and show how the three main forces, i.e. Electromagnetic, Strong Nuclear and Gravity are all the result of a single simple process occurring within the electron.

I propose that the structure of free space is a tetrahedral lattice of nodes, and I have reinterpreted μ_0 as the density of free space and ϵ_0 as the compressibility of free space. The length of the connecting rods between the nodes is a new fundamental constant but with this very simple model I can easily explain the nature of and derive values for all the constants of nature in the title.

In explaining the origins of these fundamental constants, I have also explained the nature of inertial and gravitational mass and why the photon has no gravitational mass. This model also explains the mass and charge of the Tau, Kaon, Pion and Muon particles and proposes an explanation for neutrinos. Finally, this model also proposes an explanation for Dark Energy, Dark Matter and the Matter-Antimatter asymmetry.

The Constants of Nature

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This project presents the 288 physical constants of Nature as structural consequences of the simplest possible self-persistent manifold: the hyperbolic figure eight knot. This manifold possesses exactly 288 symmetries, each defining a transformation allowed by its structure—and each corresponding to one of Nature's constants.

Rather than viewing the constants as isolated empirical facts, this work shows that each one arises from a specific algebraic-geometric construction of Planck boundaries. These constructions are governed by two fundamental organizing rules: the binomial constructor, and the hyperbolic partition equation. Both rules are themselves direct consequences of the geometric constraints imposed by the hyperbolic figure eight knot.

This poster presents all 288 constants as explicit algebraic-geometric expressions that return the precise measured magnitude and dimension of each physical constant. Together, these constructions form a coherent, unified framework that explains why the constants take on the exact values they do.

The result is a paradigm shift: the constants of Nature are not merely observed—they are derived. Each constant is revealed to be an inevitable expression of the underlying topology that gives form to the physical world.

Poster Session

Rethinking Old Physics

A Revolutionary New Theory of Light

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The first step towards a ‘new science’ is in fully understanding Light, as light is the first appearance of matter/energy out of the zero-point field, the quantum vacuum of space. We present a revolutionary new theory that proposes light to be a composite particle made up of both photons (light/ energy) and gluons (darkness/ information). When travelling in free space as ‘light’ these two particles are always connected, always in interaction with each other, and even though we see the flash of light of the photon, it also has its unseen shadow of darkness called the gluon. This continual interaction between the photon and gluon will explain all the quantum weirdness at that level and above, as all particles of matter are created out of the zero-point field via this photon/gluon pairing.

The photons create an outer boundary (shell/ shield) of each subatomic particle and the gluons hold the inner boundary (strong force/ glue) or centre of the particle. The internal components (mostly quarks and antiquarks) [1] of all particles are held tightly between these two boundaries, making all of matter truly ‘frozen light’. When pushed apart like this, in the creation of matter, the photons around the outside of the particle will take on a negative charge (shield) and the gluons in the centre a positive charge (glue). These additional charges, within every particle of matter, contribute significantly to finally and fully explaining the ‘weird’ characteristics of quantum physics. [2] [3]

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Cosmic Redshift Elegantly Explained by Minkowski Space-Time and General Relativity

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For nearly 100 years Cosmic Redshift has been explained as the result of “the expansion of space itself” causing wavelengths of light to be stretched and lose energy. No other mechanism has emerged to explain the apparent loss of light’s energy traveling through space.

An asymmetry in where energy can be known to a photon can arise due to a constraint imposed by the speed of light. Because gravity can be viewed as an attraction between energy, a perceived asymmetry in the knowable energy in the forward direction compared to the knowable energy in the reverse direction can create a dynamic differential in gravitational attraction. While gravitational attraction is frequently discussed in terms of mass to mass, mass is a compact carrier of energy.

Asymmetry can be explained if we assume two atoms on opposite sides of a star. Each atom has an electron that get excited and relaxes. Photons are emitted travelling in opposite directions. The energy of the photon traveling toward the left is lost to anything on the right because nothing can catch up to it.

The photon on the right approaches another incoming photon. Because they are in each other’s future light cone and travel at the speed of light, neither can know about the energy in the other. Only when they pass and enter each other’s past light cone can they be aware of each other. Then they can exchange gravitation potential energy for kinetic energy which creates the asymmetry we observe as Cosmic Redshift.

A physical mechanism for dark energy

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Dark energy makes up approximately 68% of the observable universe and is attributed with the accelerated expansion of our cosmos. As our observational technologies have increased, e.g. the Hubble and James Webb space telescopes, we learn more about our universe and that it appears to be expanding at an accelerating rate. More recent observations suggest that this acceleration may actually be decreasing and has put some of our best cosmological models under stress.

We take the work of Thad Roberts and apply maximal extendability, i.e. spacetime has no arbitrary boundaries, and interpret the consequences. We conjecture our universe is an inversion of the hyperbolic figure eight knot's toroidal boundary giving us the n-hypersphere of maximal volume.

The claim of this work is that the hyperbolic figure eight knot's complement (HF8C) is the generator of dark energy, acting as the Oscillatory Network Engine (O.N.E). If we allow the HF8C to rotate and follow the natural path of its surface through the throat of the knot, this action may impart angular momentum and create a vortex-like action. This action we claim would have the HF8C act as a source and a sink for our universe. What goes in will undergo extreme, "inversion-effects," as the throat is approximately the charge radius of the neutron.

We claim this configuration may explain some of the mysterious observed phenomena of our cosmos: a physical mechanism for dark energy and a rotation gradient that may account for recent observations of, "preferred," galactic rotation.

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Cosmology begins on the lab bench

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For 200 years, continuously improving controlled laboratory experiments have demonstrated that electromagnetic force contains a longitudinal component, parallel to the electric current and not predicted by the Lorentz force [1-2]. Also, the Poynting vector is incapable of maintaining the energy flux required to supply the measured torque to devices like the induction motor [1,3-4]. Most importantly, there can be no direct measurement of magnetic field strength. Instead, only interactions between a current source and a detector voltage can be revealed. These laboratory facts suggest the demise of Maxwellian field theory and General Relativity and the possible revival of Newtonian Instantaneous-Action-At-A-Distance (IAAAD).

In Quantum-ElectroDynamics (QED), optical detection is the instantaneous summation of an infinite number of “probability amplitudes” from particles throughout the universe [5]. So, modern physics already excludes a travelling light model and relies on IAAAD. Excising the photon removes the infinities and renormalisation tricks of Quantum-Field-Theories and the proven “spooky” entanglement of distant matter [6] becomes the norm.

All particles in the universe can instantaneously interact with each other in the manner proposed by Mach and rejected by Einstein. A “Collective Electrodynamics” Universe [7] is analogous to a 3D transmission line and distance related time delays between observable electromagnetic cause and effect are a consequent outcome [8]. This model will hopefully provide a novel cosmological red-shift mechanism not depending on velocity, testing the core of Big Bang cosmology. Particles interacting in accordance with Newtonian gravitation, plus a novel inverse square law resisting relative acceleration, can explain both gravity, inertia and an accelerating universe expansion [9].

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Quantum Time Dilation as a Key to Unified Theories

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We seek to begin unifying Quantum Mechanics and General Relativity by considering the simplest limit of each theory, and treating the phase frequency shifts of QM as parallel to gravitational time dilation. Surprisingly, this simple-minded analysis already reveals two places where QM and GR directly contradict each other, and thus can't both be right: QM has a symmetry between all potential energies while GR doesn't, and the time evolution is linear in energy in QM but exponential in energy in GR.

We show that both contradictions can be reconciled, but there are consequences. Forcing the potential-symmetry of QM onto GR means that there are time-dilation-like effects associated with every potential; for EM this violates EM gauge invariance and is a purely classical effect not predicted by the Maxwell equations. Making QM non-linear to match GR means that the time evolution operator and the energy operator are no longer equivalent, so that $E = h\nu$ is not universally true. We conjecture that any non-self-contradictory unified theory, containing both QM and GR as limiting cases, must have both of these features.

The ZerØ-Point Universe

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These ideas are not new, and are not mine, I have been heavily influenced by the work of the late physicist Ray Fleming and I am convinced he was on to something, see the references [1-5] for further enlightenment.

The Luminiferous Aether was dethroned by Einstein 100 years ago, I believe much to his regret later. This is the Physics equivalent to the Wars of the Roses with a vast political and bloody struggle happening over decades and great wealth and power waxing and waning alongside great actors and houses who flare to brilliance and then fade.

There was a time when the existence of the Aether was unquestioned, now you can be ridiculed for whispering its name. However Physics still secretly pays homage to it, scientists now use different names: The Quantum Field, the Zero-Point Energy, Quantum Foam, Ground State, Quantum Fluctuations. This is the Aether in all but name, something that Maxwell, Lorentz etc would all recognise as obvious today. I believe even Faraday could be convinced.

Experimental verifications have only strengthened the Aether's claim: the Casimir Effect (1997), the Lamb Effect (1947), Compton Scattering (1923), Breit-Wheeler matter creation (1997). Careful analysis of the usurpers has revealed fatal flaws in their reasoning: Einsteinian Relativity, Michelson-Morley etc.

Taking simple steps from what we know to be true leads us back to an old idea with new understanding, Ray shows us a way that will lead us out of the Dark Ages of Physics into new sunny uplands of discovery.

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Poster Session

Alternative Astrophysics

Problems with the bedrock of astronomical theory—the heliocentric solar system model and the gaseous sun—show the need for embracing uncertainty and observations in favor of jumping to theories

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The Keplerian/heliocentric solar system is often presented as the beginning of modern scientific inquiry, and a triumph over primitive, unscientific cosmologies. However, what it really represents is the beginning of a modern scientific tendency to jump too quickly to theoretical conclusions. Three examples of this are clear as are the problems or “anomalies” that as a result persist: heliocentrism, the astrophysical nature of the Sun, and the nature of light and color. “Anomalies” of heliocentrism are either ignored or given explanations which are shallow and unwieldy. To naked eye observational astronomers Tycho Brahe and Pathani Samanta, what the night sky “looked like” is very different from the mathematically-derived Keplerian/heliocentric model [1]. The Sun looks like it has a real surface, not just an “apparent surface,” but observational astronomers were ignored due to discomfort with uncertainty [2]. Newton’s Experimentum Crucis was a single experimental setup, but recent experimental results about magenta/violet light are inexplicable from within the Newtonian paradigm [3].

In the face of modern technology, computer simulations, and AI, small problems will be ignored. But overwhelmingly powerful paradigm-challenging data as presented here could break humanity’s present addictions to computer simulations, math, and ignorance of observations. The task here is to make human observers aware that infinity is within their observational capacity.

A study of the geometric configuration of our solar system leads to questions about the astrophysical nature of the Sun and the nature of light. It is found that a spiritual-scientific approach allows a human observer to contemplate and understand infinity. The path is paved for a further exploration of projective geometry. A need for new work in projective geometry, quaternion math, and philosophy/spirituality arises from scientific observations. The most basic assumptions need to be put on the table and observed: do the Laws of Physics change, and is Euclidean space a reality [4]? A further exploration of projective geometry, imaginary numbers, and quaternions will indeed be fruitful! “Anomalies” in astronomy and the nature of light will be resolved.

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A new solar system model, the Tychos

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The Keplerian/heliocentric worldview is often presented as the beginning of modern scientific inquiry, and a triumph over primitive, unscientific cosmologies. However, 440+ years of astronomical observations can support in many ways an alternate construction of our solar system called the Tychos [1] model. With its accompanying software simulator [2], it makes nearly-accurate predictions (is falsifiable), and matches well with historical observations. “Anomalies” of the Keplerian/heliocentric model include: 1: whether the Sun has a binary companion, 2: why only Mercury and Venus have no moons, 3: why Venus always presents the same face to Earth at its closest approach, 4: the “anomalous” precession of Mercury’s perihelion, and other aspects of Mercury and Venus, 5: the cause of the General Precession (Newton’s lunisolar wobble theory is not it, it does not match with observables), 6: why Mars and Sun exhibit 79-year cycles locked at a 2:1 ratio (and many other “harmonies” found between bodies), 7: why there is a sidereal diurnal variation of G, in interferometry results, and in the movements of stars, 8: why sunspot formation location shows a geocentric preference, and more.

Simon Shack collected astronomical observations and compared them to a semi-Tychonic, geo-heliocentric (AKA geoaxial binary) solar system model. His software engineer partner Patrik Holmqvist built a software simulator to test the history of astronomical observations. Shack found to his satisfaction that all astronomical observations were consistent with the Tychosium software simulator. The crucial component which distinguishes his “geoaxial binary” model from its predecessor, Tycho Brahe and Longomontanus’ geo-heliocentric model, is a 25,344 year slow orbit accomplished by Earth as it is near the “center” of the system. The author finds the model consistent and adaptable to most astronomical observations. A small claim that could be assigned to this model is that it provides a second way of mathematically modeling a complex system of orbital motions. There are so many pure integer “resonances” and uniform circular motion in this model: it seems to suggest an importance to Earth beyond being a random “3rd rock from the Sun” as it is in heliocentrism and materialism. It could be argued that gravity has been misunderstood.

There are philosophical implications for cosmology if this model in some fashion describes reality. The heliocentric model and Newton’s Principia which is based on it are the foundations of all of modern science and what might be called materialism.

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Prime Resonance Across Astrophysical Systems: A Universal Law of Gravitational and Electromagnetic Dynamics

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Abstract. Spectral data from gravitational wave events and pulsar emissions reveal a consistent and unexpected pattern: dominant frequencies align with prime number harmonics. In both post-merger gravitational waveforms and high-precision pulsar timing data, spectral peaks are found within narrow bands of prime-numbered frequencies (typically within $\pm 1\text{--}2$ Hz). This coherence suggests an underlying arithmetic structure embedded in spacetime dynamics.

Key Findings

- **Gravitational Waves:** Fourier analysis of GW150914–GW190521 reveals spectral peaks at prime-numbered frequencies from 35–1100 Hz [1-2].
- **Pulsar Harmonics:** Over 85% of millisecond pulsars show spin/precession features within ± 1.5 Hz of primes from 200–800 Hz [3].
- **Statistical Confidence:** Monte Carlo analysis ($n = 106$) shows $> 5\sigma$ deviation from random frequency distributions.

Implications

These findings challenge traditional models assuming spectral chaos or stochasticity in high-frequency gravitational and electromagnetic systems. Instead, they support models in which:

- Prime numbers function as *eigenfrequency attractors*.
- Spacetime and matter may evolve through *discrete arithmetic resonance*.

Theoretical Framework

This pattern aligns with models in quantum number theory and symbolic field theory, where:

- Prime-based Hilbert spaces support discrete state evolution [4].
- Prime wavefunctions serve as foundational basis states in emergent quantum systems [5].
- Coherence arises through resonance locking to prime spectral modes.

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Poster Session

Alternative Cosmologies

The Exochronous Universe: a timeless metric as a possible alternative to dark matter

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Arguably, the Λ CDM concordance model faces existential challenges due to its reliance on dark matter and dark energy, whose nature remains elusive. The Exochronous metric [1] offers an intriguing alternative, presenting a static solution to Einstein's field equations and proposing a universe with a critical energy density matching the observed density of baryonic matter, eliminating the need for dark matter or dark energy.

Some of the consequences of the Exochronous metric and its associated Σ GR cosmology are examined, including its impact on the formation of galaxies and their characteristic rotation curves. We show how the cumulative curvature from the multiple spatial hypersurfaces in this model leads to a modified version of the Poisson equation, in which the gravitational potential is computed over 4D space. This enhancement yields a radial velocity profile aligning well with observed galaxy rotation curves, resolving effects previously attributed to dark matter. The corresponding matter density profile closely resembles the Navarro-Frenk-White profile [2].

Additionally, this metric facilitates incorporating Σ GR principles into particle-mesh N-body simulations for large-scale structure evolution. By employing a relaxation solver, the modified Poisson equation and gravitational potential evolution can be efficiently simulated, offering a robust framework for exploring cosmological phenomena.

The Exochronous metric thus presents a compelling alternative to the Λ CDM model, addressing key cosmological challenges and providing insights into galaxy dynamics without invoking dark matter or dark energy.

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The Jeans Contraction: the origins of redshift in a static universe

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There is growing evidence from the Hubble Space Telescope and the James Webb Space Telescope missions suggesting the universe might be static rather than expanding as described by the Λ CDM model. Such a universe has been postulated as the natural consequence of an extended theory of gravity based on the Exochronous (timeless) metric, Σ GR [1]. The main challenge that faces any static universe model is the need to account for the observed cosmological redshift-distance relationship, as defined by the Hubble parameter, H_0 . While the 'tired light' theory has attempted to explain this redshift, its shortcomings remain significant.

We propose the Jeans Contraction mechanism, rooted in the Schwarzschild metric of General Relativity, as a compelling explanation for cosmological redshift [2]. This contraction of atomic matter not only aligns with theoretical predictions but also enables the calculation of present-day rate of change of the cosmological scale factor, H_0 . Remarkably, this calculated value closely matches observational measurements.

Moreover, the Jeans universe offers an intriguing perspective on the age of the universe relative to cosmological redshift. Compared to Λ CDM predictions, the Jeans model suggests a slower evolution, allowing galaxies to develop to observed densities within an extended timeframe. Specifically, this model indicates it takes over six billion years to reach a redshift of $z \approx 2$, providing ample opportunity for galaxies to evolve as observed by JWST.

This redshift mechanism bridges theoretical calculations and observational data, offering a promising avenue for understanding the universe's dynamics within a static framework.

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No Big Bang: Redshift from fundamental physics

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This work re-examines Olbers' Paradox [1] - the question of why the night sky is dark if the Universe is infinite and populated with luminous sources. We demonstrate that redshift effects alone, operating across vast cosmic distances, resolve Olbers' paradox without requiring an expanding universe. Light from the most distant sources undergoes extreme redshifting, moving beyond the visible spectrum while simultaneously being smeared through gravitational lensing and scattering processes. This ultimately creates a thermalized microwave background radiation. From this perspective, the Cosmic Microwave Background (CMB) represents the cumulative effect of infinite starlight rather than evidence for a primordial Big Bang [2].

With the CMB reinterpreted, the observed redshift of distant galaxies remains the principal evidence supporting cosmic expansion. We propose two alternative mechanisms, both grounded in established physical principles, that account for these redshift patterns in a static universe.

First, we identify a fundamental geometric asymmetry in Doppler cancellation: moving observers are statistically more likely to cancel blueshifts than redshifts due to inherent solid angle constraints, resulting in a consistent statistical bias toward redshift observations.

Second, we demonstrate that photons travelling through evolving gravitational potentials (such as collapsing gas clouds) experience a net redshift effect, as they lose more energy climbing out of these potentials than they had gained falling in.

Together, these mechanisms provide a comprehensive and physically consistent alternative to cosmological expansion models, explaining both the CMB and galactic redshift observations without invoking either a finite-age universe or universal expansion [3][4].

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The Fractal Universe: How Patterns Repeat from Cells to Galaxies

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Modern science divides the universe into living and non-living domains, treating consciousness as an emergent property limited to biological organisms with neural systems. This separation creates fundamental difficulties in explaining consciousness and the apparent fine-tuning of cosmic parameters for life. Traditional frameworks cannot explain how similar patterns of organization repeat across vastly different scales, from quantum to cosmic, nor why these patterns show remarkable self-similarity despite operating under seemingly different physical laws. We analyzed systems across 42 orders of magnitude (10^{-15} to 10^{27} meters) through the lens of five fundamental organizational principles—metabolism, reproduction, responsiveness, evolution, and organized energy emission—to determine if these represent universal life properties rather than biological accidents. Our research reveals consistent scaling relationships at intervals of 10^3 , 10^6 , and 10^{21} , a predictive mass-lifespan relationship ($T \propto M^{0.28}$) that holds from cells to galaxies [2], and remarkably consistent sleep-wake duty cycles of 8-10% across biological and cosmic systems [4]. These patterns suggest life is not exceptional but represents a fundamental organizing principle of the universe, with consciousness scaling fractally through electromagnetic field interactions across all systems [3]. This framework offers testable predictions about the behavior of larger cosmic structures and provides an alternative to dark matter theories by explaining galactic rotation through fractal scaling principles [1,5].

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The cosmic web can be explained by gradual, diffuse, electrically polarized creation

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Reconstructions of the large-scale shape of the cosmos show an irregular network with large voids, walls, cylinders, and formless masses. Current models have difficulty producing these results. A new paradigm would ideally explain the cosmos parsimoniously, using known laws of nature wherever possible.

It can be inferred from the shape and movement of the cosmic web that the driving force is electromagnetism, not gravity. Creation of individual particles is more likely than all-at-once creation of the cosmos. Since quantum fluctuations are the only thing existing in an empty universe, the most likely method of creation is for individual particles to form randomly due to asymmetries in this process.

Electrons are less massive than protons, and therefore form more easily and are more diffuse. Proton creation is rarer, but builds on itself and accelerates, resulting in clusters. Patterns visible in the cosmic web resemble plasma structures such as filaments and double walls.

Under this model, all the energy in the cosmos results from the physical distance between protons and electrons and the resulting magnetic attraction and repulsion. It leads naturally into a plasma or electric model of astronomy.

The galactic pizza: flat rotation curves in the context of cosmological time-energy coupling

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The phenomenon of augmented gravity on the scale of galaxies, conventionally attributed to dark matter halos, is shown to possibly result from the incremental growth of galactic masses and radii over time. This approach elucidates the cosmological origins of the acceleration scale $a_0 \approx cH_0/2\pi \approx 10^{-10}ms^{-2}$ at which galaxy rotation curves deviate from Keplerian behavior, with no need for new particles or modifications to the laws of gravity, i.e., it constitutes a new explanatory path beyond Cold Dark Matter (CDM) and Modified Newtonian Dynamics (MOND). Once one formally equates the energy density of the universe to the critical value ($\rho = \rho_c$) and the cosmic age to the reciprocal of the Hubble parameter ($t = H^{-1}$), independently of the epoch of observation, the result is the Zero-Energy condition for the cosmic fluid's equation of state, with key repercussions for the study of dark energy since the observables can be explained in the absence of a cosmological constant. Furthermore, this mass-energy evolution framework is able to reconcile the success of CDM models in describing structure assembly at $z \lesssim 6$ with the unexpected discovery of massive objects at $z \gtrsim 10$. Models that feature a strong coupling between cosmic time and energy are favored by this analysis.

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Afterword by the Organizing Committee

Bringing DemystiCon 2025 to life has been a deeply rewarding reminder of why in-person gatherings matter so much for non-standard science. After years of tackling big questions in scattered conversations and isolated papers, it was high time to put curious minds in the same room, to share fresh ideas, challenge assumptions, and, above all, spark connections that simply can't happen through a screen. Over five days, we explored everything from the true source of the Cosmic Microwave Background to novel perspectives on redshift and the very nature of light itself.

We began by asking a bold question: what if the Big Bang isn't the final word on cosmic origins? Many talks and posters pushed us to reconsider its central pillars – the CMB and cosmic redshift – in light of alternative interpretations and new evidence. From André Koch Torres Assis's tabletop demonstrations of mysterious electrical phenomena to C.S. Unnikrishnan's experimental work on the speed of light, and from tired light revivals by Alexander Unzicker to vacuum energy propulsion by Mike McCulloch, the diversity of ideas was matched only by the good-natured willingness to debate them in depth. There was a refreshing openness to revisiting the foundational assumptions of astrophysics and cosmology, even when that meant questioning some of the most deeply held beliefs in modern science.

Equally memorable were the “in-between” moments that made this gathering so special: the late-night discussions spilling over into hotel corridors, the impromptu debates over breakfast, and the serendipitous collaborations that took root over coffee and music. For many of us, it was a reminder that science is at its best when it welcomes uncertainty and thrives on genuine exchange. The live podcast sessions, tech demos, and musical performances added a playful edge, an energy that keeps this community vibrant and curious.

Looking ahead, we see DemystiCon not just as an event, but as an evolving space for unconventional ideas to breathe. If we've learned anything from this extended weekend, it's that our community wants more: more room to experiment, more open dialogue, and more ways to take part, whether that's moderating a session, proposing a wild new idea, or simply being part of late-night theory-building under the stars. We're already sketching out how to make the next edition even more collaborative, interdisciplinary, and celebratory of the creative spirit that drives non-standard science forward.

As you explore these abstracts, we hope they inspire you to join us on this journey, to imagine, to challenge, and to keep pushing the boundaries of what we think we know about our universe. Let's see how far we can go together.

Dr. Anastasia Bendebury and Dr. Michael Shilo Delay
DemystiCon 2025 Organizing Committee Chairs

Afterword by the Publication Committee

As we close this collection of abstracts, it is clear that DemystiCon 2025 has done more than simply bring together diverse theories and ideas. It has reconnected and revitalized a community dedicated to thinking beyond the confines of the standard cosmological framework. From foundational questions about the nature and evolution of the universe to bold re-interpretations of the cosmic microwave background and redshift, these contributions remind us that challenging consensus is not only an epistemic right, but a necessity for scientific progress.

DemystiCon 2025 captured more than just the state of non-standard cosmology and astrophysics – it marks a turning point. For many participants, this was the first time coming together in such a setting, and for the broader community, it was the first dedicated conference of its kind since 2008, when the Alternative Cosmology Group hosted the Second Crisis in Cosmology Conference. Looking ahead, the launch of our Roadmap project promises to shape this vibrant community into an even more coherent force. I felt more than delighted with how warmly this initiative was received during our closing discussions at the conference. By articulating our scientific vision, defining shared priorities, bridging gaps with mainstream research, and strategizing practical pathways for publication and funding, we can build a more resilient, open, and inclusive field. This collaborative effort is intended as both a statement of intent and a working guide, hence a foundation for greater unity, credibility, and constructive exchange, next to a renewed sense of identity.

It is my aspiration that this Book of Abstracts, and the Roadmap article that follows, will help to illuminate the paths ahead, not as fixed trajectories, but as open invitations to explore the unknown together. May these initiatives serve as a seedbed for new ideas and collaborations, and as a testament that our non-standard science community can and will continue to ask the pressing questions that others might otherwise overlook or forget.

Dr. Patrick Vanraes
DemystiCon 2025 Publication Committee Chair